

The correlations between disciplinary diversity in publications and citations

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to describe the correlations between interdisciplinary research (IDR) and disciplinary diffusion. IDR is built on references (papers cited by an article) and created by scholars. Accordingly, there are two approaches for evaluating IDR: the disciplinary diversity of the reference list and the disciplinary diversity of the author's affiliations list. The disciplinary diversity of citations (papers citing a given article) reflects disciplinary diffusion, which classifies into intra- and inter-disciplinary diffusion by comparing this given article. To explore the correlation between IDR and intra- and inter-disciplinary diffusion, we selected 234,689 nanoscience papers from the Web of Science core collection and calculated the four discipline diversity indexes (i.e., variety, balance, disparity, integrated diversity) in IDR and citation for correlation analysis. The results show there are significant positive correlations between the disciplinary diversity of IDR and citation, where IDR in the reference dimension has a stronger correlation than that in the affiliation dimension. Further, interdisciplinary diffusion is associated with more subjects but intradisciplinary diffusion relates to fewer subjects. IDR has a stronger correlation with intradisciplinary diffusion, especially intradisciplinary diffusion in the first year.

Introduction

Many scientific challenges are naturally complex, rarely utilizing a single discipline to address an issue (Ledford, 2015; Okamura, 2019). Interdisciplinarity is a necessary way to explore and answer scientific questions more thoroughly. Accordingly, interdisciplinary research (IDR)(Porter, Roessner, Cohen, & Perreault, 2006) has attracted much attention from both academics and government entities. A key goal is the identification of the key mechanism that makes IDR successful.

To assess IDR, scholars have proposed several metrics. A series of indexes of disciplinary diversity proposed by Stirling (2007), which is used extensively, includes variety, balance, disparity, and integrated diversity. To increase the distinction of interdisciplinary, Zhang improved integrated diversity indexes and proposed Ture diversity (Zhang, Rousseau, & Glänzel, 2016). In addition, there are two perspectives for measuring IDR: the disciplinary diversity of reference list and the disciplinary diversity of authors' affiliations (Abramo, D'Angelo, & Zhang, 2018; Liu, Chen, & Bu, 2022; Zhang, Sun, Chinchilla-Rodríguez, Chen, & Huang, 2018). References (papers cited by an article) reflect the disciplinary knowledge base cited by authors in a publication, where interdisciplinarity is measured by the level of diversity within the references (Zhang et al., 2016). Scholars producing new work, show the disciplinary scientific collaboration, where interdisciplinarity is measured by the level of diversity within the coauthors (Abramo, D'Angelo, & Di Costa, 2012). In terms of disciplinary diffusion, citations (papers citing a given article) reflect the diffusion of knowledge, where

interdisciplinarity is assessed by the level of diversity within the citations (Rodríguez, 2017; Stopar, Drobne, Eler, & Bartol, 2016).

Furthermore, interrelationships in discipline diversity are measured by utilizing these four metrics (Karmakar, Singh, & Pinto, 2020). Zhang, Sun and Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al. (2018) explore the relationships of those four disciplinary diversity metrics in the affiliations and references. However, additional research is needed to further study these correlations. In disciplinary diffusion, scholars focus on the relationship between interdisciplinarity and citation impact where interdisciplinarity with different disciplinary distances (Larivière, Haustein, & Börner, 2015), with different citation time windows (Chen, Song, Shu, & Larivière, 2022) are studied. However, the correlation between disciplinary diversity and discipline diffusion needs to be explored in more detail.

In this paper, we select 234,689 papers in nanoscience fields from 1999 to 2015, from the Web of Science (WoS) core collection. We calculated the disciplinary diversity of papers using the four metrics: variety, balance, disparity, and integrated diversity. Disciplinary diffusion is classified into intra- and inter-disciplinary diffusion at reference and affiliation levels. Then, we analyze the correlation between disciplinary diversity in IDR and their diffusion by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient of four disciplinary diversity metrics of IDR reference, affiliation and citation.

Data

Publication data was downloaded from the WoS core collection provided by the Indiana University Network Science Institute (IUNI). There are 84,087,016 papers with WoS categories from January 1900 to March 2022, that are affiliated with the 21 disciplines according by Journal Citation Reports, and 280 sub-disciplinary categories (regarded as subject) used by WoS.

Papers on nano are collected in 1999-2015, limited to the nanoscience and nanotechnology field. There are 234,689 unique publications on this topic with DOIs, 2,578,724 references and 1,971,546 unique cited papers in a 5-year citation window, including 44, 278, and 266 unique publication subjects respectively. There are 187,338 unique affiliations producing these focal papers, with 15 unique affiliation subjects. An affiliation disciplinary dictionary is built with 366 keys and corresponding affiliation subjects (shown in Table 1).

Table 1. Description of dataset.

<i>Dataset name</i>	<i>Data size</i>	<i>The number of covered subjects*</i>
Publication	234,689 papers	44 (PS)
References	2,578,724 papers	278 (PS)
Citations	1,971,546 papers	266 (PS)
Affiliation	187,338 affiliations	15 (AS)

Note: * “PS” refers to publication subject and “AS” refers to affiliation subject.

Methods

The IDR and diffusion model

Figure 1. The IDR and diffusion model.

Scientific papers include two activities: production and citation (Cerovšek & Mikoš, 2014). Publication production is built on citation references (papers cited by an article) and presents new work created by scholars. Citations (papers citing a given article) represent the diffusion. IDR is assessed by the disciplinary diversity of references list and the disciplinary diversity of co-authors' affiliation respectively. The disciplinary diffusion includes intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion, which is measure by the intra- and interdisciplinary cited papers at the reference and affiliation level respectively (shown as Fig 1.) Disciplinary diversity can be measured by four discipline diversity indexes, i.e. variety, disparity, balance and integrated diversity.

Discipline diversity index

The variety (V) is used to measure the number of distinct subject categories in a paper. V is computed as,

$$V = \sum SC_i \quad (1)$$

Where SC_i in references and publication ranges from 1 to 255 (number of WoS sub-categories) and SC_i in affiliations from 1 to 13 (number of WoS categories). $SC_i = 1$ represents existent WoS category and $SC_i = 0$ represents nonexistent WoS category.

The balance (B) refers to the evenness of different disciplines in a paper. B is calculated as,

$$B = 1 - \frac{\sum(2i-V-1)x_i}{V\sum x_i} \quad (2)$$

where i ranges from 1 to V and x_i is the frequency count of i^{th} in increasing order.

The disparity (D) is defined as the distinct of the subject categories in a paper. D is computed as,

$$S_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sqrt{TR_i \times TR_j}} \quad (3)$$

$$d_{ij} = 1 - S_{ij} \quad (4)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{V(V-1)} \sum d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where S_{ij} is the Salton similarity between SC_i and SC_j , computed by cross-citation similarity matrix, which has rows (i.e., each publication) and columns (i.e., each subject). As for publication discipline similarity, publications have references, which are published in the corresponding journal, and the journals are classified into 280 different subject categories. As for affiliation discipline similarity, based on the above, the journals are grouped into 21 broad categories. C_{ij} is the total number of rows (i.e., publications) that SC_i and SC_j co-occur. TR_i is the sum of SC_i column. Note that $S_{ii} = 1$.

The integrated diversity (*ID*) is considered a single value to measure all three individual indexes. The equation is as follows:

$$ID = \frac{1}{\sum p_i p_j (1 - d_{ij})} \quad (6)$$

where $p_i = x_i/X$, $X = \sum x_i$, d_{ij} is the dissimilarity between SC_i and SC_j , calculated from formula (4).

Table 2. Variable and explanation.

Variable	Explanation
V(<i>i</i>)	Variety index
B(<i>i</i>)	Balance index
D(<i>i</i>)	Disparity index
ID(<i>i</i>)	Integrated diversity index
Y(<i>i</i> , <i>j</i>)	The number of intradisciplines of citation at <i>i</i> level in the <i>j</i> th year
NY(<i>i</i> , <i>j</i>)	The number of interdisciplines of citation at <i>i</i> level in the <i>j</i> th year.
T5(<i>i</i>)	The total number of intradisciplines of citation at <i>i</i> level in 5 years.
TN5(<i>i</i>)	The total number of interdisciplines at <i>i</i> level in 5 years.

Note that *i* refer to IDR and citation, including references(r), affiliations(a), cited papers(c). *j* range from 1 to 5.

Correlation analysis

In this paper, we study the correlations between disciplinary diversity in IDR and disciplinary diffusion, including correlations between four discipline diversity indexes in IDR and (1) integrated diffusion, (2) intra- and interdisciplinarity diffusion at reference and affiliation level (shown in **Table 2.**)

Results

Correlations between disciplinary diversity in IDR and citation

Figure 2. Pearson correlation between four disciplinary diversity indexes in citing references, affiliations, and cited papers. Note that all correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (3-tailed).

Fig. 2 describes the correlations between disciplinary diversity in IDR and citation at four disciplinary diversity indexes (i.e., variety, balance, disparity and integrated diversity) level, respectively. The significantly positive correlations between disciplinary diversity in IDR and citation at four levels are released. Furthermore, there are strong positive correlations between

disciplinary diversity in references and citations, with 0.4, 0.15, 0.34, 0.26 coefficients, corresponding to variety, balance, disparity, integrated diversity.

Correlations between IDR and intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion at different levels

Figure 3. The total number of papers with intradisciplinary diffusion and interdisciplinary diffusion at different levels. (A) Reference level. (B) Affiliation level. X-axis refers to the number of subjects of diffusion at reference or affiliation level, Y-axis refers to the number of publications. Blue plots and orange plots show the intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion correspondingly.

Fig. 3 compares the distribution of subjects to papers across two aspects of IDR (reference and affiliation) for intra- and inter-disciplinary diffusion. There are more articles with intradisciplinary diffusion than those with interdisciplinary diffusion in fewer subjects. Articles with interdisciplinary diffusion are associated with more WoS subjects, having a long tale for highly interdisciplinary diffusion. At the reference level, intra- and inter-disciplinary diffusion show similar distributions (rising then falling) at different peaks, corresponding to 3 and 9. At the affiliation level, articles with intradisciplinary diffusion show a decrease from a peak of 1 subject, while those with interdisciplinary diffusion rise to a peak at 6 subjects and then fall.

Fig. 4 presents there are significant correlations between IDR and disciplinary diffusion over time. In a 5-year citation window, discipline diversity has a stronger correlation with intradisciplinary diffusion than interdisciplinary diffusion. At the reference level, IDR correlates positively with intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion, with the exception of a negative correlation between the balance of IDR and intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion. At the affiliation level, IDR correlates negatively with intradisciplinary diffusion with the exception of a positive correlation between the variety of IDR and intradisciplinary diffusion. IDR correlates positively with interdisciplinary diffusion with the exception of a negative correlation between the balance of IDR and interdisciplinary diffusion. Furthermore, with increasing years, IDR shows stronger correlations with intradisciplinary diffusion in the first year than those in later years. The variety of IDR is positively correlated with intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion but the balance of IDR is negatively correlated with those. The disparity of IDR is positively correlated with intra- and interdisciplinary diffusion, with the exception of a negative correlation with intradisciplinary diffusion at the affiliation level.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation coefficient between discipline diffusion and discipline diversity index of publication production. (A) Reference level. (B) Affiliation level. Note that all shown correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (3-tailed).

Conclusion

The primary objective of this study is to analyse and visualize the correlation between disciplinary diversity in publication production and citation. Study results show disciplinary diversity of IDR is significantly positively correlated with citations, especially the disciplinary diversity of IDR in the reference dimension. In terms of disciplinary diffusion, papers with interdisciplinary diffusion relate to more subjects but a larger number of papers with intradisciplinary diffusion relate to fewer subjects. There are stronger correlations between IDR and intradisciplinary diffusion, especially in the first year. In future studies, the correlation and causation by regression analysis and analysing different subject data should be reviewed to determine correlations between disciplinary diversity in publication production and citation in different subjects.

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